

Scoliosis assessment from trunk rotation based on torsobarography using machine learning

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Abstract: An Angle of Trunk Rotation (ATR) over 7° is a common indicator of scoliosis. Torsobarography as a novel surface topographic system for radiation-free posture analysis is capable to quantify the asymmetry of the trunk. This study investigates on 71 subjects the potential of torsobarography to differentiate between $ATR < 7^\circ$ and $ATR \geq 7^\circ$ using machine learning algorithms. A Cohen's Kappa κ of 0.76 was achieved for an optimized classifier model. However, a generalizability verification revealed an average κ of 0.54. In conclusion, the rotation of the trunk can be characterized by machine learning algorithms based on torsobarographic images.

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I. Introduction

The Angle of Trunk Rotation (ATR), measured by a scoliometer, is a common indicator for assessing trunk symmetry. It is applied for radiation-free screening and monitoring of scoliotic spine deformities [1]. From a cut-off $ATR \geq 7^\circ$, there is a high probability that treatment of the scoliosis is required [2, 3]. Surface topographic systems for analyzing the back surface have potential to provide more detailed information and greater accuracy in the radiation-free assessment of scoliosis [4]. Torsobarography, a novel surface topographic system, examines the pressure distribution of the trunk in a lying position and derives anatomical back morphology [5]. In addition to surface topography, torsobarography utilizes information from the mass distribution of the trunk, which can be caused by vertebral rotation in scoliosis. This effect is visualized in Figure 1. This study investigates the ability of torsobarography to distinguish between ATR levels above and below 7° using machine learning algorithms.

Figure 1. Side-by-side comparison of torsobarography resulting pressure images of a) $ATR < 7^\circ$ and b) $ATR \geq 7^\circ$

II. Material and methods

71 subjects (40 females, 31 males) were examined in the study and categorized into two levels based on the ATR measured by scoliometer: $ATR < 7^\circ$ (22 females, 19 males, mean = 4.5° , range: 2° to 6°) and $ATR \geq 7^\circ$ (18 females, 12

males, mean = 9.4° , range: 7° to 20°). The dorsal pressure image of each subject was recorded utilizing a high-resolution pressure mapping system (LX100:100.160.05, XSENSOR). The subjects were placed on the sensor array according to a standardized measurement procedure, as shown in Figure 2 [5].

Figure 2. Measurement setup of the torsobarography [5]

A total of 39 parameters for each pressure image were extracted (based on [5]) to characterize the dorsal trunk morphology and asymmetry. These parameters constituted the metric input features for modelling the classifier. All features were standardized. A stratified 5-fold cross-validation was applied for the following classification models: k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN), Decision Tree (DT), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Naive Bayes (NB). The hyperparameters of the models were optimized by grid search, evaluated by Cohen's kappa κ (shown in Table 1). Kappa was interpreted by criteria used by Landis and Koch [6] to categorize model performance regarding inter-rater reliability: slight ($0 \leq \kappa \leq 0.2$), fair ($0.2 < \kappa \leq 0.4$), moderate ($0.4 < \kappa \leq 0.6$), substantial ($0.6 < \kappa \leq 0.8$) and almost perfect performance level ($0.8 < \kappa \leq 1$).

Table 1. Optimization range of hyperparameters during grid search for: kNN, DT, SVM and NB

Model	Hyperparameter	Range (Step Size)
kNN	Number of neighbors k	1 to 15 (1)
DT	Minimum leaf size	1 to 10 (1)
SVM	Kernel function	POLY: cubic polynomial, RBF: radial-basis-function
	Regularization C	1 to 4 (0.5)
NB	Kernel smoother	Gaussian

The grid search was combined with a sequential forward floating selection (SFFS) to identify a local optimal feature space (FS). The accuracy (ACC), sensitivity (SEN) and specificity (SPC) were utilized to further compare the results. The stratified 5-fold cross-validation was randomly repeated 50 times to assess the generalizability of the models.

III. Results and discussion

Comparing the results in Table 2 of the optimized models indicates that the SVM performs best according to all evaluation metrics. SVM-POLY achieved a substantial inter-rater reliability with κ of 0.76 as well as an ACC of 88 %, with a near-perfect SPC of 98 % and SEN of 77 %. SVM-RBF had a similar performance but a higher SEN of 90 %. In addition, SVM-RBF required the smallest FS of 5 features to attain the local optimum (cf. Figure 3). The findings from kNN and DT are identical apart from the selected FS. Depending on the optimization criterion κ , the worst result was delivered for the NB with κ of 0.64. Nevertheless, all models exhibit a substantial performance level according to κ .

Table 2. Evaluation metrics for optimized models from 5-fold stratified cross-validation

Model	κ	ACC	SEN	SPC	FS
kNN	0.68	0.85	0.83	0.85	7
DT	0.68	0.85	0.83	0.85	9
SVM-POLY	0.76	0.88	0.77	0.98	7
SVM-RBF	0.74	0.87	0.90	0.85	5
NB	0.64	0.83	0.70	0.93	8

Figure 3. SFFS of the best models: kNN (Number of neighbors $k = 4$), DT (Minimum leaf size = 4), SVM-POLY (Regularization $C = 1$), SVM-RBF (Regularization $C = 4$), NB (Gaussian)

The evaluation of results in Table 3 revealed that none of the models maintain their performance across different random combinations of the folds during cross-validation. A significant decrease in model quality was noted for the

kNN and DT, which can now only be categorized in a fair performance level. Furthermore, the SVM provided the best and most robust model to classify the two ATR levels with torsobarography, achieving an average κ of 0.54 and thus a moderate model performance.

Table 3. Mean value and standard deviation of evaluation metrics after 50 times random stratified 5-fold cross-validation

Model	κ	ACC	SEN	SPC
kNN	0.33 ± 0.08	0.68 ± 0.04	0.55 ± 0.05	0.77 ± 0.05
DT	0.24 ± 0.11	0.63 ± 0.06	0.60 ± 0.09	0.64 ± 0.07
SVM-POLY	0.52 ± 0.07	0.77 ± 0.04	0.67 ± 0.06	0.84 ± 0.05
SVM-RBF	0.54 ± 0.07	0.77 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.07	0.80 ± 0.04
NB	0.42 ± 0.07	0.73 ± 0.03	0.59 ± 0.04	0.82 ± 0.05

Overall, ATR level classification is limited by the size of the available dataset. Nevertheless, actual results of the SVM are already relevant and suggest that a larger and more varied database should lead to better and more robust model performance. Therefore, the torsobarography is capable to recognize different ATR levels using machine learning algorithms, which underlines its application as a tool for screening and monitoring of scoliosis.

IV. Conclusion

This study has demonstrated for the first time that torsobarography parameters for the characterization of dorsal trunk morphology can be successfully utilized to classify different ATR levels using machine learning algorithms. Future research needs to investigate further associations of torsobarography with the characteristics of scoliotic deformities of the spine.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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